

STUDYING THE UNDERSTANDING OF DIABETIC PATIENTS WITH REGARD TO INSULIN HANDLING AT DIABETIC CLINIC

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Abstract

Insulin therapy is crucial for diabetes management but requires patients to have sound knowledge of insulin handling. Safe practices include correct storage, accurate administration, site rotation, and safe disposal. Poor practices may lead to serious complications like hypoglycemia, hyperglycemia, and infections.

Aim & Objective: This audit aimed to assess the understanding and practices regarding insulin handling among diabetic patients attending the OPD at Social Security Hospital Shahdara. It also evaluated patients' knowledge about storage, administration techniques, and their improvement after educational interventions.

Methodology: A questionnaire containing 20 questions was administered to 50 diabetic patients. Data was collected both qualitatively and quantitatively. Quantitative data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel, while qualitative responses were reviewed by two independent researchers.

Results: The average participant age was 50.2 years, all with Type II Diabetes. Among them, 36% had diabetes for over 10 years. Only 38% were aware of insulin side effects, while 98% knew about correct storage. Hypoglycemia was reported by 24% in the past 6 months. Blood sugar monitoring was inconsistent, with only 16% checking levels before every insulin dose. Regarding injection practices, 54% cleaned the site before use, 70% used the correct 90° angle, and all participants avoided syringe sharing and practiced site rotation.

Conclusion: The audit identified strong awareness of insulin storage and syringe safety but highlighted gaps in knowledge about insulin side effects, regular glucose monitoring, and proper injection site hygiene. These findings stress the need for continuous patient education and regular reinforcement to enhance safe insulin use and improve diabetes outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Insulin therapy requires patients to have a thorough understanding of how to handle insulin safely and effectively. This includes knowledge about correct storage, accurate administration, proper dose adjustment, and safe disposal of insulin needles and containers. Mismanagement in any of these areas can lead to significant health risks, including hypoglycemia, hyperglycemia, and infection.

In an outpatient department (OPD) setting, it is essential to ensure that diabetic patients are well-educated about insulin handling to maintain their health and prevent complications.

AIM & OBJECTIVE:

The primary aim of this audit is to evaluate the Understanding and practices related to insulin handling among diabetic patients in an outpatient department (OPD) of Social security Hospital Shahdara. This includes assessing patients' knowledge of proper insulin storage conditions to ensure its efficacy and safety. Moreover, It also involves evaluating their proficiency in administering insulin, focusing on correct injection techniques and site rotation to prevent complications.

Finally, the audit will measure improvement by reassessing patients' knowledge and practices after the educational interventions to evaluate the effectiveness

of these programs and ensure ongoing enhancement of diabetes management.

Methodology:

Data Collection:

Through qualitative and quantitative research methods, including a questionnaire analysis consisting of 20 questions, we aim to capture the variable experiences of Diabetic patients. By engaging directly with patients, we seek to observe the understanding, handling practices and proper disposal to insulin among diabetic patients

Data Analysis:

The collected data is qualitative and quantitative. Quantitative data is analysed on Microsoft Excel version 2404 by one researcher. Qualitative data is assessed by two researchers separately.

Results

A total of 50 responses were collected in written form. The patient attended their general medicine Out patient department for Anti-Diabetes medication at Social Security Hospital Shahdara, after which they were approached to participate in this audit. They were explained what the audit was about, and informed consent was taken.

Average participant age was 50.2

All of the patients were Diabetes type II. 36% has had diabetes type II more than 10 years, while 28% diagnosed in between one to five years, 28%

diagnosed in between 5 to 10 years and only 8% has had Diabetes in less than a year.

60% participant mentioned , they were not aware of the side effects of the insulin , while 38% were aware of the side effects of insulin. Apart from one

participant all were aware to keep the insulin vial at cool place I.e fridge.

Participants were asked if they had any hypoglycemic event in last 6 months ,74% did not experience any hypoglycemic event, 24% mentioned of the hypoglycemic event and one participant was not sure of the event. Additionally , they were asked about

either they check the expiration date before the use of insulin vial; 68% said they do check expiry date before insulin use, while 28% said no and 2 participants said sometimes the do check.

Participant were asked if they have access to the glucometer:84% has access to the glucometer ,12% had no access to the glucometer .Those , who had

access to the glucometer were asked about , how many times do they check the blood sugar . we found that only 16% check the blood sugar every time before

insulin administration , 8% check once a day ,30% check 1 to 3 times and 46% check sometimes before insulin.

Participant were asked ;do they clean site before insulin administration, We found out 54% clean the site before using the insulin syringe and 46% said no. Moreover , on asking the method of cleaning the

syringe site ,26% clean the site with alcohol swab, 55% with cloth , 15% with wter while the rest use different way.All were aware of not sharing the syringe with others.

Participants were asked about the angle technique to use for insulin syringe. We found out 70% administer insulin syringe at 90* angle while rest use other than

90* angle.Everyone was aware to change the syringe spot.

This audit aimed to evaluate the knowledge and practices of patients with Type II Diabetes regarding insulin administration, safety, and self-monitoring of blood glucose levels at the Social Security Hospital Shahdara.

Discussion:

Patient Demographics and Diabetes Duration:

The findings reinforce the widely acknowledged benefits of Diabetic patients in Out door department. The average participant age was 50.2 years, reflecting a population typical for Type II Diabetes. A significant portion (36%) had been living with the condition for over 10 years, indicating a well-established history of diabetes management among many respondents. Moreover, a smaller group (8%) was relatively new to diabetes care, having been diagnosed within the past year.

Awareness and Education:

Furthermore, a notable finding was that 60% of participants were unaware of the potential side effects of insulin. This suggests a gap in patient education, which is critical given the potential risks associated with insulin therapy. However, nearly all participants (98%) were aware of the need to store insulin vials in a cool place, demonstrating good adherence to storage guidelines.

Hypoglycemia and Self-Monitoring:

Regarding hypoglycemia, 24% of participants reported experiencing a hypoglycemic event within the past six months, highlighting the importance of ongoing education on managing and preventing hypoglycemia. While 84% of participants had access

to a glucometer, only 16% consistently checked their blood sugar before each insulin administration. This low rate of consistent blood glucose monitoring may increase the risk of insulin dosing errors and associated complications.

Injection Practices:

When it came to injection site hygiene, only 54% of participants reported cleaning the site before administering insulin, with a variety of methods used, including alcohol swabs (26%), cloth (55%), and water (15%). This indicates variability in understanding and applying best practices for injection site preparation, which could impact the risk of infection.

The majority (70%) administered insulin at the correct 90-degree angle, suggesting good adherence to recommended injection techniques. Additionally, all participants were aware of the importance of not sharing syringes and rotating injection sites, which are critical aspects of safe insulin administration.

Conclusion:

The audit reveals both strengths and areas for improvement in patient education and practices related to insulin use. While participants generally demonstrated good awareness of storage practices and syringe safety, there were gaps in knowledge regarding insulin side effects, consistent blood glucose monitoring, and proper injection site preparation. These findings underscore the need for targeted standards to enhance patient safety and optimize diabetes management outcomes. Further training and regular reinforcement of best practices could

significantly improve the quality of care and reduce the risk of complications among this patient population.

References:

- Montoya, J. M., Thompson, B. M., Boyle, M. E., Leighton, M. E., & Cook, C. B. (2021). Patterns of sharps handling and disposal among insulin-using patients with diabetes mellitus. *Journal of diabetes science and technology*, 15(1), 60-66.
- Lamont, Tara, et al. "Safer administration of insulin: summary of a safety report from the National Patient Safety Agency." *Bmj* 341 (2010).
- Dimitriadis, George D., and John E. Gerich. "Importance of timing of preprandial subcutaneous insulin administration in the management of diabetes mellitus." *Diabetes Care* 6.4 (1983): 374-377.
- Bukhsh, Allah, et al. "Type 2 diabetes patients' perspectives, experiences, and barriers toward diabetes-related self-care: a qualitative study from Pakistan." *Frontiers in endocrinology* 11 (2020): 534873.
- Ahmed, Muhammad Umer, et al. "Knowledge, Attitude, and Self Care Practices Amongst Patients With Type 2 Diabetes in Pakistan." *Global journal of health science* 8.7 (2016): 1.
- Hodge, Robert H., et al. "Multiple use of disposable insulin syringe-needle units." *Jama* 244.3 (1980): 266-267.